

Polarized intensity (mJy beam⁻¹)

0.24 0.26 0.28

54°32'30"

19 $z_{\text{Sp}} = 0.7523$

Dec (J2000)

00"

31'30"

100 kpc

00"

16^h18^m36^s 33^s 30^s 27^s

RA (J2000)

